

Multipurpose Solarized Crop Transplanter

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Abstract— India is one of those countries where mechanized processes in the agriculture sector are being adopted at a rapid pace. Most crops especially rice, are labour driven and require about 70-85 labour days per acre. Since large workforce is involved in agriculture, the process becomes time consuming and expensive. Nowadays it has become difficult to obtain labour and water at the right time for various activities of farming. Thus, to conquer these problems there is a requirement of mechanical tools in the field of crop cultivation. One such tool being a mechanical crop transplanter. The focus of this machine is to develop a machine which will address issues faced by farmers in terms of manpower and resources. This paper is aimed towards a transplanter which is based on a simple four bar mechanism and runs on solar power. The mechanism includes a crank, which is rotated with the help of a DC motor. The crank moves the rocker link with the help of a connecting rod. The connecting rod is used as the picking arm to plant the seedlings into the ground. Using the connecting rod as picking arm is more efficient than using the rocker because the connecting rod can perform general motion. The motor is powered by a rechargeable battery, which can be charged by the help of solar energy as well as through domestic power supply. This transplanter will be very economical for small scale farmers who are planning to start farming and are looking for relatively cheaper methods of cultivation.

Keywords—Transplanter, four-bar mechanism, solar, multipurpose.

I. INTRODUCTION

Crop transplantation is perhaps the most crucial method where small seeds are sown at one place and they are transplanted to another field after the seeds take the form of small seedlings after attaining a certain age. This is often arranged in the form of drains to get higher renounce and less weeding. Furthermore, harvesting of prior crop and planning of the substrate and transplantation should be done in a small time period in multiplied planting by doing customary way of transplantation, it would be hard. These variables appear the require for mechanization of transplantation even more than before. Labor costs, timing in transplantation and the depth at which seedlings ought to be planted are some of other factors that indicate the necessity of fully loaded mechanized transplanter in the field of agriculture.

Although the conversion of manual transplantation into mechanized transplantation would, to some extent lead to the reduction in demand of labour but it would also result in maximum efficiency along with minimum damage to the seedlings. However, this requirement happens when the labour's income is less than the revenue provided by machines replacement. Nowadays Indian farmers are inclined towards adopting new agricultural methods along with new technologies. Hence in this paper main focus is on crop transplantation machine which could give a colossal breakthrough to the agribusiness segment particularly in the field of crop cultivation. A crop transplanter is a special equipment which is best suited to the transplantation of small seedlings on marshy paddy fields. Machine transplantation of the crops is one the most effective alternatives to manual transplantation, since it can achieve less labour cost, timely transplantation

and optimum plant density which eventually lead to higher productivity. Between 1990 and 2000, a rapid development and growth in the spread of machine transplantation was witnessed in India. According to the latest technological developments in the agriculture sector such mechanization of crop transplanting machines will surely fulfil the requirements and move past the problems cognated with manual transplantation. Hence, the cultivation of crops will be continuous and the future demands will be met along with the continuous supply of crop in certain volumes.

II. AIM & OBJECTIVE

The main motive behind this paper is to study and analyze the voids in researches between the use of traditions like manual transplantation methods and the machine transplantation of crops in India, along with the valid dimensions related to the ongoing transplantation machines. At present, in India a few farmers are actually aware about different ongoing transplanters, their pros and cons and their necessity so as to improve fertility and increase the farmers profit. Hence, we aim to study about crop transplanters, their merits and necessity and want to help to spread awareness about transplanters in our nation so as to reduce the expenditure involved in farming and improve the properties of crops.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

In this paper various parameters regarding mechanized transplanters have been studied, their importance in the real world has been discussed and attempts have been made to improve the efficiency of the transplanters in the real world. One can understand the definition of transplantation in the following manner. Transplantation is the process in which seedlings about 22-30 cm tall and 25-35 days old are uprooted from the nurseries either manually or mechanically and planted in some other field. In India farmers cultivate rice during the Kharif season. Most of the manual transplantation is done by female workers. S. Pradhan and S.K. Mohanty (2014) conducted an experiment involving 15 female subjects of varying ages. In their experiment, 4 push, 3 push and 2 push transplanters were utilized and it was concluded that 3 push rice transplanters performed the best leaving all other transplanters behind.

Similarly, Rajvir Yadav (2007) made an attempt to evaluate the 6-row crop transplantation machine which was hand operated. The farm extent of the transplantation machine was beyond their imagination. It was more than the conventional strategy. The average force required for pulling the transplanter was 129.92 N for male and 144.32 N for female subjects. Martin and Chaffin (1972), Ayoub and McDaniel (1974), and Chaffin (1983) found that heights at which push-pull forces are applied are the most important parameter which largely affect the average force output.

The SRI (System of Rice Intensification) transplantation technique says that the seed plantation should be done one hill at a time and a space of 25x25 cm should be maintained for better utilization of water, nutrient and pest control.

In a similar study conducted by G. Singh in 1985 at an IIRRI farm a mechanized rice transplanting machine came

up with a field capacity of 0.034ha/h under different conditions of deepness of water and seedlings of varying age.

A.K. Goel in 2008 conducted an experiment with 3 transplanting machines which were OUAT, CRRI and Yanji transplanters. He came to a conclusion that a sedimentation period of 32 hours and the same for 56 hours was suitable for a manual and Yanji transplanters respectively.

The SRI technique of cultivation is more economical to paddy farmers when compared to the traditional manual transplantation, as was concluded in 2013 in an economic analysis conducted by Rampuram Jayapal Reddy & Dr. N. Sandhya. They focused this test in the Mahabubnagar of Andhra Pradesh. It was found out by Baldev Raj Kamboj in 2013 that that deterioration of ground is a result of excessive puddling. Keeping in mind this previous analysis and the problems associated with manual transplantation, the need of machine transplantation becomes relevant day by day. Machine transplantation is less labour intensive and optimum plant population can be achieved.

IV. COMPONENTS OF CROP TRANSPLANTER

1. Chain
2. Sprocket
3. Shaft
4. Crank
5. Coupler
6. Picking arm
7. Tray
8. Tray support
9. Frame

V. CONSTRUCTION

1. **Chain:** In this mechanism, we have a simple chain to transmit torque from driver to driven sprocket.

2. **Sprocket:** In this mechanism, two sprockets are needed, one at the motor and another

at shaft.

3. **Shaft:** The main function of the shaft is to provide motion to the crank.

7. **Tray:** Tray holds the seedlings in place while the rocker pushes them into the ground.

4. **Crank:** This is first link in our 4-bar mechanism. Crank is supposed to move in full rotation and provide motion to the coupling link.

8. **Tray Support:** It is part of the frame and holds the tray in one place.

5. **Rocker:** This is fourth link in the mechanism. It transmits motion from the crank to the coupler. It is attached to the frame and the coupler.

9. **Frame:** Frame acts as the fourth link in our 4-bar mechanism. On this every component is mounted.

6. **Picking Arm:** This is the coupler our mechanism. It performs general motion and pushes the seedlings into the ground.

VI. WORKING

The main purpose or operation of this machine is transplanting. In this process, premature crop seedlings are kept on a tray. These seedlings are pushed into the ground with the help of a picking arm which is performing general motion, i.e., translation and rotation. In our mechanism, the connecting rod is used as the picking arm rather than using the rocker. It is because the connecting rod can perform general motion in a crank-rocker mechanism. By this general motion not only the seedlings

can be pushed into the ground efficiently but also the soil can be ploughed a little to make space for the next batch of seedlings.

The picking arm/connecting rod is connected to a rocker which is mounted on the frame on the other end. The crank moves the coupler. The crank is mounted on a shaft which by a DC motor with the help of chain and sprockets.

We are also trying to make this mechanism run on solar power which would be highly efficient for the farmers.

VII. INSTANTANEOUS CENTRE DIAGRAM FOR VELOCITY ANALYSIS

So, the length of the links will now be as follows:

- Link AB = 1.8cm
- Link BC = 12.6cm
- Link CD = 2.8cm

No of links in the mechanism, N=4

No of I- Centre in the mechanism,
 $= N(N-1) / 2$
 $= 4(4-1) / 2$
 $= 6$ links

i.e. $\begin{matrix} 12 & 13 & 14 \\ & 23 & 24 \\ & & 34 \end{matrix}$ (I – Centre)

$13 = 12, 23 \text{ or } 14, 34$
 $24 = 13, 34 \text{ or } 12, 24$

(12, 13, 23) & (13,14,34) will be collinear
 According to **Kennedy’s Theorem**.
 Similarly, (24,23,34) and (12,14,24) will be colinear.
 Let,

- ω_2 = Angular velocity of crank – 2
- ω_3 = Angular velocity of coupler – 3
- ω_4 = Angular velocity of rocker – 4
- V_B = Absolute velocity of the point- B
- V_C = Absolute velocity of the point- C

From the Figure:

- Distance, $I_{12} - I_{23} = 1.8\text{cm} = 45.0\text{mm} = 0.045\text{m}$
- $I_{13} - I_{23} = 15\text{cm} = 15 \times 25 = 375\text{mm} = 0.375\text{m}$
- $I_{13} - I_{34} = 18\text{cm} = 18 \times 25 = 450\text{mm} = 0.45\text{m}$
- $I_{14} - I_{34} = 2.8\text{cm} = 70.0\text{mm} = .07\text{m}$

Velocity at point B,

$V_B = (I_{12} - I_{23}) \times \omega_2$
 $V_B = 0.045 \times 289.288$
 $V_B = 13.018 \text{ m/s}$

Velocity at the point B is also,

$V_B = (I_{13} - I_{23}) \times \omega_3$
 $\omega_3 = 13.018 / 0.375$
 $\omega_3 = 34.715 \text{ rad/s}$

Velocity at point C,

$V_C = (I_{13} - I_{34}) \times \omega_3$
 $V_C = 0.45 \times 34.715$
 $V_C = 15.622 \text{ m/s}$

VIII.CALCULATION OF VELOCITIES OF DIFFERENT LINKS BY I-CENTRE METHOD

Operating speed of the motor = 850 rpm = N_1
 No of teeth on the sprocket attached with the motor,
 $T_1=13$

No of teeth on sprocket attached to the shaft, $T_2=40$
 By chain sprocket formula,

$N_1 T_1 = N_2 T_2$
 $N_2 = N_1 T_1 / T_2$
 $N_2 = (8500 \times 13) / 40$
 $N_2 = 2762.5 \text{ rpm}$

Angular velocity of the crank,

$\omega_2 = 2\pi N_2 / 60$
 $\omega_2 = (2\pi \times 2762.5) / 60$
 $\omega_2 = 289.288 \text{ rad/sec}$

Let the scale be,
25mm = 1cm

Also,

$$V_C = (I_{14} - I_{34}) \times \omega_4$$

$$\omega_4 = 15.622 / 0.07$$

$$\omega_4 = 223.171 \text{ rad/s}$$

Hence, the angular velocity of:

$$\text{Crank, } W_2 = 289.288 \text{ rad/sec}$$

$$\text{Coupler, } W_3 = 34.715 \text{ rad/sec}$$

$$\text{Rocker, } W_4 = 223.171 \text{ rad/sec}$$

All in clockwise Direction.

IX. BENEFITS OF A LOW COST TRANSPLANTER

1. Labour cost is saved leading to less overall cost of production, thus implying the efficient utilization of resources.
2. Seedlings are timely transplanted at the right age.
3. Uniform spacing and plant density is maintained by a machine transplanter.
4. Higher productivity compared to traditional methods.
5. Root injury in seedlings is drastically reduced leading to less diseases in the seedlings.
6. Pudding is eliminated which eventually leads to a better soil health.
7. The rural youth enjoys several benefits through machine transplantation, the most important one being a source of backup cash-flow.

X. CONCLUSION

In this paper it was concluded that tall work request amid the crest periods unfavorably influences the convenience of operation, subsequently diminishing the crop yield. To counterbalanced these issues, mechanical transplantation is the answer. The workload statistics and the position of labour in the agricultural sector is affected by mechanization. Consequently, there's a requirement of machine transplantation in crop development segment. In this direction transplanters help us to perceive a vivid prospective. Ongoing transplanting machines are highly complex and difficult for most farmers to maintain. Therefore, it is our aim to create such a transplanter which can be easily used by any farmer and is hassle free in terms of service and maintenance. The fundamental complication, as discussed earlier, with the existing transplanters is that, they are exceptionally costly. Besides they have exceptionally complex component which cannot be fixed or overhauled effortlessly at a general repair shop. For farmers in India who are just getting into farming, a crop transplantation machine would prove to be a boon. Decreased cost of manpower, exponential growth in productivity and less health risk are some of the reasons why machine transplantation will prevail in India.

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